

Extraction and carrier facilitated membrane transport studies of some biologically important metal ions (Na^+ , K^+ and Ca^{2+}) using redox switched ionophore

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Abstract : Supramolecular chemistry has evolved from efforts to mimic the non-covalent interactions and the phenomenon of molecular recognition in biological systems. Membrane transport study is one of the important applications of supramolecular chemistry. Redox switched ionophore 1-anthraquinonyloxy pentane has been synthesized and used as carrier for transport and extraction studies of some biologically important metal ions (Na^+ , K^+ and Ca^{2+}) through chloroform bulk liquid membrane system. The sequence of metal ions extracted in oxidised state and reduced state by ionophore was $\text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+$ and $\text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{K}^+$ respectively. The order of metal ions transported by ionophore was found to be $\text{K}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{Ca}^{2+}$ and for $\text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{K}^+ > \text{Na}^+$ respectively. The extraction results reveal that ionophore is selective for Na^+ in oxidised state and for Ca^{2+} in reduced state. The carrier ability of ionophore to transport metal ions is more for K^+ in oxidised state and for Ca^{2+} in reduced state.

Keywords : Redox switched ionophore, extraction, membrane, transport studies.

Introduction

Alkali and alkaline earth metal ions (Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+}) play a vital role in biological systems as charge carrier in nerve impulse and help in maintaining membrane potential across cell membrane¹. The liquid membrane system have much importance as models for some biologically important alkali and alkaline earth metal ions transport across bio-membranes and helpful in understanding complex behaviour in biochemical transport processes. Bulk liquid membranes are often used to simulate biological membrane functions². Research concerning selective transport of metal ions through liquid membrane using glymes, polyethylene glycols and non-cyclic synthetic receptors as carriers has been reported^{3,4}.

The anthraquinone moiety has proven to be the most versatile and useful redox active group in biological and chemical system^{5-7,1,4}. Crown ether derivatives containing anthraquinone moiety were studied for cation binding and redox coupling^{7,13}. Keeping these studies in view, we have synthesized redox switched ionophore based on anthraquinone derived podands as earlier been reported⁸. For the first time we have used anthraquinone moiety

containing hydrophobic side arm for the extraction and transport studies of some biologically important alkali and alkaline earth metal ions across chloroform bulk liquid membrane system. Isolation studies of the metal salt with ionophore have also been reported.

Materials and methods :

Metal picrates and salts were prepared as reported earlier⁸. The reagents used in synthesis are 1-chloroanthraquinone, sodium hydride (Merck), pentanol (Fluka). The solvents CHCl_3 , CH_2Cl_2 and THF (Qualigens) were used as obtained. Flame photometer (Systronics) was used for the estimation of metal ions.

Synthesis of ionophore :

A solution of pentanol (1.56 ml) in THF (10 ml) was added to vigorously stirred suspension of NaH (60% in 0.24 g) and mixture was refluxed for 30 min as shown in Scheme 1. Then a solution of 1-chloroanthraquinone (2.42 g) in THF was added to it and refluxed at 80 °C for 10 h with stirring. The reaction was carried out under N_2 atmosphere. The reaction mixture was concentrated and then residue was mixed with CH_2Cl_2 , and then washed with water and then with brine. The organic phase was

separated and dried over (MgSO_4), filtered and concentrated, purified by column chromatography (silica gel, 2% $\text{MeOH}/\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$) followed by recrystallization with CH_2Cl_2 /hexane/ethanol and characterized by m.p., TLC, IR and ^1H NMR spectral analysis, m.p. : 138 °C; Yield : 3.76 g (75.6 %); IR of ionophore (KBr) ($\nu \text{ cm}^{-1}$) : 2924 ($\text{CH}_3\text{-CH}_2$ -), 1680 (C=O), 1272 (Ar-O-CH_2), 854 (ArH); ^1H NMR of ionophore (δ in ppm) : 3.35–4.40 (8H, m, O-CH_2), 2.14–1.99 (3H, m, CH_3), 7.20–8.35 (7H, m, Ar-H); IR of NaOnp complex (KBr) ($\nu \text{ cm}^{-1}$) : 2910 ($\text{CH}_3\text{-CH}_2$ -), 1674 (C=O), 1266 (Ar-O-CH_2); ^1H NMR of NaOnp (δ in ppm) : 3.95–4.85 (8H, m, O-CH_2), 2.10–1.84 (3H, m, CH_3), 7.95–9.00 (7H, m, Ar-H); IR of KDnp complex (KBr) ($\nu \text{ cm}^{-1}$) : 2915 ($\text{CH}_3\text{-CH}_2$), 1673 (CO), 1267 (Ar-O-CH_2); ^1H NMR of KDnp (δ in ppm) : 3.85–4.81 (8H, m, O-CH_2), 2.12–1.90 (3H, m, CH_3), 7.40–8.70 (7H, m, Ar-H).

Extraction studies :

In the extraction studies, 10 mL of $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ aqueous solution of metal salts (Na^+ , K^+ and Ca^{2+}) and 10 mL of $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ of ionophore in chloroform were vigorously stirred in a 50 mL beaker for 4 h on a magnetic stirrer. The amount of metal ion in the aqueous phase was initially determined. After 4 h, the depleted aqueous phase was estimated using flame photometry.

Transport studies :

Transport studies were performed in a U-tube glass cell also known as "Pressman cell" at room temperature⁹. The $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ of ionophore in 15 mL of chloroform was placed in the bottom of the "U" tube serving as the membrane. The 10 mL of $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ of aqueous solution of metal salts was placed in one limb of the U-tube serving as the source phase and 10 mL of double distilled water, placed in another limb of the U-tube, which served as the receiving phase. The membrane phase was constantly stirred using magnetic stirrer for 24 h. The

samples were withdrawn from both the phases and analyzed for the amount of metal ions transported.

Results and discussion

Blank experiments of extraction and transport studies for each metal salt in which membrane was devoid of carrier were performed. No leakage of cation from source phase into organic phase was observed. All measurements were performed in duplicate to check reproducibility.

In order to find out the optimum concentration of metal ion for transport and extraction studies, we have varied the concentration of metal ions from 1.0×10^{-1} to $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, keeping the concentration of ionophore constant ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$) in both oxidised and reduced states. For optimization of the ionophore, the concentration was varied from 1.0×10^{-1} to $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, keeping the concentration of metal ions constant ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$). The optimised concentration for metal ions and ionophore was reported $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ respectively.

As is evident from Table 1, the sequence of metal ion extracted with ionophore in oxidised and reduced states was $\text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+$ and $\text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{K}^+$ respectively. The ionophore has been found selective towards Na^+ and Ca^{2+} . The selectivity ratio for $\text{Na}^+ : \text{K}^+$ is 2.31 : 1 and for $\text{Ca}^{2+} : \text{K}^+$ is found to be 12.5 : 1 respectively. This selectivity is due to small size with high charge density of Na^+ which is responsible for its self encapsulation and formation of stable complex^{10,11}. A comparative study of IR spectra of ionophore and their metal complexes re-

Table 1. Amount of metal cations extracted with redox switched ionophore (P_1) into organic phase after 4 h in chloroform

Metal salt concentration = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, ionophore concentration = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ in (15 ml) chloroform

Sl. no.	Metal salt	Oxidized form (ppm)	Reduced form (ppm)	Selectivity ratio	
				Oxidized form	Reduced form
1.	CaDnp	-	-	-	-
2.	CaOnp	1.3	5.0	-	12.5 : 1 ^b
3.	KDnp	2.6	-	-	-
4.	KOnp	1.3	-	-	-
5.	KPic	-	0.4	-	-
6.	NaDnp	6.0	-	2.31 : 1 ^a	-
7.	NaOnp	1.0	-	-	-

^a $\text{Na}^+ : \text{K}^+$; ^b $\text{Ca}^{2+} : \text{K}^+$.

veals a shift for quinonyl carbonyl and side arm at 1680 (C=O) to 1674, 1676, 2910 and 2915 cm^{-1} for NaOnp and KDnp respectively. The shift in ^1H NMR peaks (OCH_2) has been reported at 3.95–4.85 and 3.85–4.81 ppm for NaOnp and KDnp complexes respectively. Stoichiometry of isolated complexes have been given in Table 2. The data of isolated complexes shows the par-

Table 2. Properties of isolated complexes of metal salt with redox switched ionophore

Metal salt	Solvent	M.p. (°C)	Stoichiometry
NaOnp	Methanol	232	2 : 1
KDnp	Benzene	228	1 : 1

icipation of the donor oxygen sites of quinonyl carbonyl and side arm of the ionophore during complexation enhances metal binding property^{10,12}.

The results of transport studies are tabulated in Table 3. The trend of metal ion transported with ionophore in oxidised and reduced state is found to be $\text{K}^+ > \text{Na}^+ >$

Table 3. Amount of metal cations transported with redox switched ionophore into aqueous phase after 24 h in chloroform
Metal salt concentration = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, ionophore concentration = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ in (15 ml) chloroform

Sl. no.	Metal salt	Oxidized form (ppm)	Reduced form (ppm)	Selectivity ratio	
				Oxidized form	Reduced form
1.	CaDnp	0.1	20.0	–	7.4 : 1 ^b
2.	CaOnp	–	15.8	–	–
3.	KDnp	–	2.7	–	–
4.	KOnp	1.2	0.4	1.2 : 1 ^a	–
5.	KPic	1.0	0.2	–	–
6.	NaDnp	–	–	–	–
7.	NaOnp	1.0	–	–	–

^a $\text{K}^+ : \text{Na}^+$, ^b $\text{Ca}^{2+} : \text{K}^+$.

Ca^{2+} and $\text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{K}^+ > \text{Na}^+$ respectively. It is observed that ionophore is selective for K^+ and for Ca^{2+} . The selectivity ratio for $\text{K}^+ : \text{Na}^+$ is 1.2 : 1 and for $\text{Ca}^{2+} : \text{K}^+$ is found to be 7.4 : 1 respectively. The hydrophobic side arm of the ionophore permits easy passage of metal-ionophore complex from the organic phase to the aqueous receiving phase and results in the effective release of metal ions in the receiving phase. The an-

thraquinone derived ionophores containing simple glymes, glycols, single and double armed podands are found to possess more extraction ability in comparison to present ionophore containing hydrophobic side arm^{10,12,14}. In contrast, ionophore possesses better transportability due to increased hydrophobicity of the side arm. The side arm with no donor sites is responsible for less extraction. The possibility of intramolecular hydrogen bonding between hydroxyquinone hydrogen of the anthraquinone and oxygen of side arm is more in reduced state that enhances its selectivity.

Conclusions :

From the above discussion, it can be concluded that the ionophore shows good transport efficiency for Ca^{2+} and behaves as a selective extractant for Na^+ . This piece of work emphasizes the ability of the synthesized ionophore to recognize biologically important metal ions but acts as better carrier in chloroform bulk liquid membrane system. The objective of this precedent research work is to find out the applicability of designed receptor for the separation of metal cations and biomolecules by affinity chromatography. This work paves the way for the designing of ionophores having side arm without donor sites with variable chain lengths and highly hydrophobic to facilitate transport across organic membrane system.

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